

A Systematic Literature Review of Green Ports Strategies in Sustainable Port Planning

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

1. Introduction

Ports are considered vital national infrastructure and significant for economic growth, and shipping companies are under - pressure to resolve the adverse impact on the environment and society created because of port operations and development (Puig et al., 2014). In global maritime organizations' policy discourse, the Green Port concept has recently emerged to address the ports' ecological and social sustenance problems (Pavlic et

ABSTRACT

The increasing global concerns such as climate change and energy use, port activities, and environmental effects have grown in recent years. As it is subject to a closer review of governing ecological enforcement, the port industry faces increasing challenges. Many attempts to promote sustainability such as green ports, sustainable ports. However, existing planning remains an issue for sustainable ports and green ports to achieve sustainability effectively. Through a literature review, this thesis aims to address these issues in sustainable port planning. Sustainable port planning and sustainable growth, and addressing generational demand for environmental protection strategies are essential findings. We propose bringing environment-friendly perspectives on sustainability from a maritime supply chain viewpoint into port planning. On this basis, the Green Port definition is suggested. This research offers detailed and comprehensive knowledge of green port strategies for sustainable port planning to overcome the global environmental challenges and sustainable development.

Keywords: GREEN PORT, SUSTAINABLE PORT, PORT PLANNING, SUSTAINABILITY APPROACH, LITERATURE REVIEW

al., 2014).

Many scholars, especially marine engineers, social scientists, maritime economists, and many others from different life courses, have attracted a lot of attention to the green supply chain concept as we refer to it in this paper. In the general context of this development, it should be noted that port management's function and governance within and across regions has become more diverse in the previous twenty years (Lee & Lam, 2016).

Most of the European ports, like the Bremen Ports, are additional to the two-hybrid management systems are organized in collaboration with the tenant model have thus been combined. Although this paper does not concentrate on new governance structures, it is crucial to remember that port authorities have shuffled themselves and play the role of a manager in all aspects of port operations and activities relating to port operations. In the Western African and European ports under research, the tenants enforce eco-friendly port policies individually and in partnership with commercial vessel owners. They play both the role of tenants and legislators.

2.0 Literature review

2.1 Current ideas related to the green port, eco-centric port, and durable port

Different international organizations held a crucial conference that connected the ports to environmental sustainability in 1993. Various global development organizations narrated it. Regarding the fulfillment of people's needs, renewable ports have since drawn a lot of interest to environmental management. Different groups suggested that in 2013 the ecological marine area needs to be centered on the "Working with Nature Philosophy," "Corporate Social Responsibility," "Green Economic Growth Strategy," and "Participation of Stakeholders." As far as eco-ports are concerned, the European Ship Port Association (ESPO) has initiated a venture designated Eco Ports, which has developed as an ecological friendly port (Puig & Darbra, 2019).

At the beginning of the 21st century, the definition of "green port" was commonly adopted as a mixture of concerns related to the ecology and financial needs. It was proposed by the PIANC group of workers that the ecological ports should realize the coordination between the human user and the environmental issues. Also, they should regulate the idea of nature ("PIANC-Sustainable Maritime Navigation").

2.2 Shipping emissions

Various conventions discuss ecological hazards in the maritime arena. The given strategies or routines are developed throughout time, including multiple concerns about maritime emissions, such as toxins, oil pollution, water pollution, etc. (Lister et al., 2015). The global organizations have selected areas to control emission with the landmark of about 0.1 percent Sulphur since 2008. The sulfur content borderline of 0.5 percent is supposed to be effective by 2020, compressed from the present 3.5 percent borderline.

NOx is always addressed. The Vessel Resource Performance Maintenance Project addresses it. We cannot find any CO2 limit yet, which is globally imposed by any organization. These enforced conventions have resulted in different shipping pollution control science, such as the verification of a new benchmark for ships that could help make shipping more ecologically stable or the option of other routes (Psaraftis & Kontovas,

2010). Different tech-related concerns add retrofitting of automated engines, more efficient hulls, and updated propulsion versions (Eide et al., 2009).

The given topics expose an increasing interest in more ecologically appropriate vessels. On the other hand, excessive environmental demands may manipulate ship-authorities because of the high price of installation requests.

Subsidies are starting to be provided by a variety of port authorities for eco-friendly ships. An example is that the World Port Climate Initiative (WPCI), considered several 55 ports worldwide, conducts different ecological activities, such as vessel discounts above a specific measurement on the Environmental Ship Index. For example, a collaborative program, the 'Green Flag Incentive,' was initiated by the Port of Long Beach, which established opportunities for the ships incoming to the port to minimize their velocity in the port territory. It is one of the most crucial frameworks available to ports to cut up excess vessel emissions (Ahl et al., 2017) (Winnes ct a1., 2015). The At-Benh Rule also makes it mandatory to use port-based electronics to reduce or neutralize emissions for all vessels calling at California ports in 1 January 2017.

2.3 Port activity

Reducing the use of energy in ports by using sustainable transportation like electric or fuels in port operations and producing renewable energy sources in ports are some of the core strategic decisions for port activities (Acciaro et al., 2014). There are different other probable solutions. They include strategies for wastage management and reuse. They have sewage, ballast water, noise, spills, disturbance, and particles emitting from maintenance activity, according to Lam and Notteboom, 2014. There is also marine habitat, wetland, and coastal erosion-related ecosystem restoration (Lam and Notteboom, 2014) (Chen and Pak, 2017). Instances of these kinds of landmarks are the capacity of excavators to conserve energy generated when a container is sunk, and it is in use of fuel-powered trucks on the shore (Hu et al., 2017). Different ports have been using the latest and more comfortable clean machinery to minimize cargo handling equipment emissions. For example, it is used in the Los Angeles ports.

In developing nations, challenges are mainly the result of the high benefit of conventional policy adoption. Keualj and Traven (2017) mentioned the idea of installing a shore-based power generation system in Croatia. Still, it was noticed that the absence of interest and the high maintenance cost is rejected. Operational and management issues in other circumstances are more important to the obstacles. Klopott (2013) has shown that different ports have aligned with economic legislation since entering the EU in 2004. They are very active in environmental protection, including surveillance of their water management and emissions and some investments in technological advances. However, instead of heading further than that point, they still mostly follow the EU's criteria. Barnes-Dabban et al. (2017) investigated the based composite on ports' perception in organizations adapting to the phenomena of 'Green Port' in West and Central Africa.

The paper showed that flexible and adaptable administrative steps and a tradition of conversational and advisory management helped transform the 'green port' concept into business fundamentals. The port authority underwent a structural transformation with increased private sector involvement from a working port to an

authoritative port.

2.4 Inland transport system

Several reports have been written on CO₂ and other external cost reductions via mode shapes port-inland link shifts in recent decades. Janic (2007) established a standardized accounting domain model for intermodal road transport, for instance, air quality, sound, traffic fatalities, and pollution. Janic and Vleugel (2012) showed real-life management of environmental impacts. Sanchez Rodriguez et al. (2015) showed that re-routing shipments away from conventional large ports in the south-east of the UK could dramatically reduce total Carbon emission. Still, they suggested it would be necessary to achieve this goal to optimize the flow of cargo transportation among ports and inland origins through a more vertically integrated supply chain.

Policymakers have implemented subsidies and legislation in some areas to remove barriers to accelerated linear adjustments in the port hinterlands. Targeted funds and other programs for the construction of port developments, rail and inland waterways linking to ports in the EU will be used to fund ports if they can be shown to contribute to a shift in treatment method. Different groups or organizations have been set up as the cornerstone of European transport development, focusing on intermodal routes throughout Europe. As far as the pre-establishment of port-inland transportation in developing nations is involved, there has been little research on the topic, specifically into the port's role. However, another analysis has been carried out on corridors. For instance, Regmi and Hanaoka (2013) explored reducing emissions through a modal shift on passages between Laos and Thailand.

Gonzalez-Areual et al. (2018) illustrated in their global analysis that very few ports in industrialized countries had taken measures to boost sustainable developments in their Hinterland. Thus, every move towards decreasing emissions from container handling results from a modal shift from road to rail, driven by the Government's structural improvement of railway operations and infrastructural development.

2.5 Environmental impact on ports

Although sailing constitutes a cornerstone of ports' business activities and represents an essential role in driving economic development in the surrounding areas, it isn't easy to measure the environment's impact at these locations. GHG and carbon emissions may be generated from fuel consumption during shipping. Still, the disadvantages of in-port marine activities related to the natural environment and human life are more complex evaluation tools. A problem solver is supposed to be the port area, which provides national interference management between the territory and territorial water.

According to many experts (Boscarato, 2015; Bergqvist, 2012; Chiu, 2014), air pollution, greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, leakage of liquid waste, light pollution, generation of solid and hazardous waste, soil depletion, environmental problems that usually affect port. The issues are grouped into three subcategories in a project led by the OECD (Oecd.org., 2017):

1. Problems created by ships approaching the port at sea
2. Problems caused by port operations
3. Intermodal transport emissions and networks serving system the Highlands Port

3.0 Current practice in port planning

3.1 Master planning

Israel's two main ports on the Mediterranean Sea, named Ashdod and Haifa's ports, deal with the Israel Strategic Port Development (IPC, 2005). It refines the lengthy requirement for shore facilities and the alternatives provided to satisfy these specifications.

The port Master Plan's significant uncertainties are identified as further demand on future vessel size, space requirements for the port extension, and possible operating procedures. The 50-year forecast is popular in using as the basis for planning. A significant emphasis of the Maasvlakte 2 Structural Plan was versatility. The Master Plan's strategy is to build your future, i.e., the client should be provided absolute versatility in designing his terminal on Maasvlakte 2 (Rotterdam Mainport Development Project, 2008).

It recognizes that the best way to work with potential confusion is to develop sustainable projects acceptable for different futures. The primary scheme cycle has been set up whereby the Master Plan is adapted to the newest insights each year. The Master Plan becomes more comprehensive with each process as more information becomes accessible.

3.2 Engineering design

The structural framework is usually sorted out by engineers who receive functional specifications set out in a 'terms of reference' document from the client (port owner or port authority). They focus on converting these applicable requirements into technical specs and designing based on these deterministic statistics, the infrastructure system elements using rules and expectations. Besides, experts in the engineering section should not label these forecasts as volatile predictions of future demands and resources. They are likely to result in designs being insufficient and inadequate in the long run.

Developing fixed requirements is firmly embedded in the technological project's full development process (de Neufville, 2004). The properties of materials and the loads on structures typically refer to unknown building factors. (Minimum) compliance with the applicable specifications and guidelines by which safety factors are prescribed to be incorporated in designs shall be considered.

3.3 Project evaluation

In the case of government funding, significant projects related to the infrastructure, such as port projects, economic impact markets, and a cost-benefit analysis for evaluating infrastructure spending, are required (from a broad welfare economy perspective). Any output of an investment project can be routinely calculated and a currency value allocated where appropriate. The report typically uses mono usage cost and benefit figures and uses techniques.

Most investment products consider the only aspired result (e.g., expected benefit or cost of capital). Research can deliver policymakers with minimal guidelines, including supplying them with simple prediction models. By the way, it helps them analyze uncertain circumstances, e.g., maximum, minimum regret, and equal probability rule (Thomas and Maurice, 2005).

The new financial resources do not trust consistency. Furthermore, the sequential decision-making method, North American Academic Research, 4(2) | 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4540675> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 89

including the alternatives' working prototype, is incorporated by the primary evaluation. The elaborated structural framework of the chosen option and the ultimate progress of the implementation) does not spare any space for a flexible alternative to be included in the project's initial evaluation defined during the detailed design phase. It could lead to mistaken decision making.

3.4 Green and sustainable port planning

The fundamental concept of sustainable development is that there is no need for disparate and overlapping environmental conservation priorities and business goals (Barbier, 1987). The idea of sustainability can be described in terms of the three pillars of sustainability (3BL): economic growth, environmental quality, and social justice (Elkington, 1997). Savitz and Weber (2006) indicated that conservation requires conducting an enterprise so that it causes minimal harm to live beings concerning corporate profitability. Sustainability is seen as a combination of environmental, social, and economic demands and an equitable balance between the three dimensions that foster long-term organizational competitiveness (Sikdar, 2003; Carter and Rogers, 2008).

Any green policies to be successful in business can contribute to the commercial aspect of improving economic performance (Rao and Holt, 2005). Anderson and Brodin (2005) stressed the value of active customer engagement to recognize the customer requirements and what they expect in ecological problems. Dougill et al. (2006) affirmed and stated that taking local wishes and concerns into account at an early level would improve the project's design and increase the likelihood of successfully meeting local needs and priorities.

There is proof that connecting conservation goals and strategies to business policy helps integrate durability into what the organization does and its stakeholders and customers (Wagner, 2011). Proactive organizational planning and concrete commitment contribute substantially to conservation, often in a written environmental strategy (Ramus and Steaer, 2000).

The given constructs are suggested to be added to the green and sustainable port system based on a literature review and case studies.

Figure 1: Green and sustainable port framework

4.0 Research methodology

The literature review was recognized as a crucial scientific apparatus to build a knowledge base for an empirical investigation as a scientific proof approach (Tranfield et al., 2003). A literature review, which involves the data collection methods, optimizing the initial investigation output, and evaluating the residual literature, has become famous for its comfortable and easy-to-copy function (Wu et al., 2018). This thesis approaches through a systematic approach to the literature review to manage and describe the literature with analyzing the content to interpret specific findings and detailed discussion (Wu et al., 2018).

In this study, a couple of data sources are checked for heavily publicized Scopus database publications. Expert consultants select the authoritative websites of local and foreign organizations from representatives of sustainable port representatives. The keywords "green port," "sustainable port, " and "planning " were used separately for the two-part search.

Figure 2: Number of Publication on Port

The Scopus quest obtained green port planning, sustainable planning, and eco port planning as of 10 January 2021. (1) Electricity, (2) Earth and Planet related Sciences, (3) Computer Study (4) Biological Sciences and Agrotechnology, (5) Materials the official website quest found science, (6) Mathematics, (7) Physics and Astronomy, (8) Molecular Biology and Biochemistry, (9) Chemical science (10) Arts and Humanities, (11) Immunology and Microbiology, (11) Besides, 15 documents related to the planning of a long-lasting port, eco-port, and green port.

5.0 Result and discussion

5.1 Contribution of shipping lines

As mandated by international regulations, several techniques are already being implemented by shipping lines to decrease their impact on the environment, primarily concerning reducing pollution. The main important thing to consider first is the used fuel. Heavy fuel oil is an output of the refining strategy. It appears to rely on ocean-going vessels, which are very budget-friendly and the most polluting fuel. (Cullinane & Cullinane, 2013).

Vaporized petroleum energy is considered to be the most viable alternative fuel. LNG is cheaper than HFO, and MGO relative to traditional petrol has no PM or SOx emissions and a much smaller NOx though it

generates a 25 percent CO₂ decrease. The shortage of refueling facilities is a crucial obstacle to LNG's widespread use, but this can improve as costs rise and the Member States' response to the EU promotes LNG bunkering facilities.

Some other followed methods are being covered, but they stay in their primary stage. People have been considered Hydrogen as a wonderful fuel for diverse forms of transportation for some options. Hydrogen only emits water vapor, which is a possibility from an environmental point of view. At the same time, biofuels are considered a new fuel method for several modes of transport. In the shipping industry, they can be mixed with traditional fuel. Still, concerns about processing and land use propose that biofuel is not an important area to collect energy for maritime activities (Cullinane and Cullinane, 2013).

Other pollution control measures involve slow steaming and strengthened hull design, in addition to alternative fuels. A velocity lowering of 20 % would decrease energy usage by approximately 40 percent and CO₂ by about 7 %. Cariou (2011) found that the slow steaming process contributes to an 11 percent reduction in CO₂ output from containerships in the years following the economic downfall.

5.2 Contribution of ports

Emissions from vessels at ports are gradually becoming a problem, notably for NO_x, SO_x, and PM, which affect the local community's health. Vessel pollution in ports is generally managed by cold ironing, LNG use, and speed reduction in ports. Shoreside electricity or Cold Ironing is when ships are connected to shoreside electricity at the berth to provide hotel power instead of running their auxiliary generators. Winkel et al. (2016) claimed that it would be possible to save an achievable amount of EUR 2.94 billion in health costs and a significant reduction of 800,000 tons carbon emissions if all European ports use coast-based electricity.

WPCI (2017) says that only twenty-eight ports are organized globally with cold ironing shows us how sloth the procedure has been so far. Installation costs and the need to install the linking technology onboard each vessel are the biggest obstacles, which they will only do if they are likely to use it more often. On the opposite side, it won't decrease engine noise like cold ironing, and there are costs for vessels to adjust their engines. Likewise, slow steaming contributes to reducing fuel usage and emissions. However, the gatherings or collecting are not the same at lower speeds, significantly below the vessel's actual speed (Winnes et al., 2015). Energy originated directly by port operations affects fewer overall emissions. Still, different approaches may be used to counter them, even though only a tiny number of ports count their emission generally.

5.3 Action in the hinterland

To examine land transport's ecological productivity to and from ports, very little research has been done. However, this component of port operations leads to several externalities, notably congestion and local pollution. (Bergqvist and Engels-Zandén, 2012; Bergqvist et al., 2015.)

Usually, all environmental impacts are assessed and held responsible for inland vehicle estimates; the vehicle industry is held accountable for around a quarter of gas output in Europe. Inland port transport emissions, however, occur solely because of the port's operating system. There is an evolving structure of works on ecological ports, which is very little mingled with the hinterlands. Nearly none of the small number of papers

that compile lists of potential steps for green ports in the current literature includes hinterland interventions such as modal modification, except for Lam and Notteboom (2014) and Acciaro et al. (2014b). According to a review (Gonzalez-Aregall et al. 2018), the global port set and discovered that 76 out of 365 ports in different regions were reviewed were functioning as a green port hinterland strategy. These ports' most common aim in the green Hinterland was to reduce air pollution through monitoring programmes. Congestion of land and modal transition scored high as priorities, but addressing noise in hinterland transport had much lower importance.

5.4 Efforts of sustainability planning in ports

It is initially formulated by different policies and strategies for long-lasting port development as early as 1993 [19] and implemented the Ecological Ports Tools and Certification strategies in Europe [21]. According to the Urban Harbors Institute (UHI) at the University of Massachusetts, Boston, they offer planning on environmental protection and technological essentials for American green ports by 2000 [13].

Much attention has been paid to the provision by world associations and regional governments of guidelines for the scheming of green ports, long-lasting ports, and eco-ports over a couple of decades ("Urban Harbors Institute. America's green ports: Environmental management and technology at US ports"), and several similar planning initiatives have been carried out for particular ports, such as the Port of Long Beach and the Port of San Diego ("Port of Long Beach. Green Port Policy"). Furthermore, the researchers paid attention to the analysis and assessment of ports' current environmental performance status and offered sustainable or green port planning steps and ideas (Schipper et al., 2017).

5.5 Approaches to port planning for sustainability

The steps to long-lasting green port planning and sustainable planning can be presented here based on the written documents.

5.5.1 Green port planning

- In 2000, an approach to the ecological maintenance of American green ports was proposed by the Urban Harbors Institute of the University of Massachusetts, Boston, including the elimination, avoidance, minimization, mitigation, or remediation of environmental impacts associated with ports' construction and activity ("Urban Harbors Institute-America's green ports").
- The Port of Long Beach, in 2005, adopted green port policies through the introduction of specific environmental standards, the setting of goals, the establishment of detailed metrics for evaluating progress towards achieving the targets, the creation of ecological measures and particular incentives, and legislative proposals ("Port of Long Beach. Green Port Policy").
- In 2006, the Port of Sydney made recommendations for creating green ports, including environmental and commercially viable techniques and practices [30].
- To construct an ecological port, the San Diego Unified Port District has set a timeline and targets for water condition improvement, energy conservation, air pollution, waste reduction, sustainable

development implementation, and staff and public awareness. ("Board of Port Commissioners. Green Port Program").

- The Maritime and Port Authority of Singapore in 2010, urged ocean-going ships to eliminate emitted particles like nitrogen oxides and sulfur oxides to use pure and clear fuels to reach the green port (Lam & Notteboom, 2014).
- In 2014, the Department of Transportation of Jiangsu Province released the Action Plan on the validity of three years for the Construction of Green Ports in Jiangsu Province (2018-2020) and this Rested Green Action to implement national strategies, including energy conservation, emission control, pollution reduction, and preservation of shoreline resources (Wu et al., 2020).

5.5.2 Sustainable port planning

- In 1993, UNCTAD introduced the Ports Sustainable Development Planning Strategy, which offers the project objectives and pre-feasibility analysis of the primary environmental assessment. (Wu et al., 2020).
- In 2013, the PIANC guided port authorities to establish sustainable ports, including the notion of long-lasting ports planning to compensate the requirements of present and future generations, the analysis of the roles of the authorities, the identification of ecological and sustainability issues in shores and related logistics connections and the formulation of strategies ("PIANC-Sustainable Maritime Navigation")
- In 2018, the International Association of Ports and Harbors (IAPH) was established a world port sustainability policy to implement the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The software will interconnect the objectives and missions with different projects and programs will be developed ("International Association of Ports and Harbors").

6.0 Identified challenges in port planning and future outlook

The main idea in maritime areas is economic entities. They are not interested in bearing expenditure. Therefore, it is necessary to understand the struggles and limitations and the possible political and operational scenarios. This involves applying already established best practices and more stringent regulations to enable sooner implementation of new technologies and the transition to green-based approaches. This paper purposes of deepening understanding within a planned context to encourage decision-making and consider what can and should be done.

Under current conditions, the marine sector's decarbonization remains impossible without a significant decrease in shipping volume. It is an awe-inspiring choice to turn a share of the world fleet to LNG and widespread slow steam adoption at sea. Significant steps can be taken in ports, which are the main focus of this paper, such as converting in-port operations to electricity and managing ship emissions by combining slow steaming at the port, using LNG, and cold ironing. Other incentives, such as port dues and goals for inland modal transition, may also make a significant contribution to reducing ship and inland emitted particles.

The last research question is about sustainability. It is crucial to address the problem by stock holders and policymakers. Is the mitigation of emissions merely a potential addition to be calculated and considered, or should it be an essential step to internalize the extra cost? The container shipping revolution has ensured that marine shipping costs are just a portion of today's total cargo cost. On average, transport costs only 3% of the value of goods worldwide. The figure is even lower for some consumer goods, so an increase in freight rates will undoubtedly be absorbed due, for example, to a bunker levy facilitate the move away from HFO.

The shipping industry's air and other environmental contamination is not a new issue, and the resources of research carried out and seen in this volume are already enough to inform action. This paper illustrates the port authorities and legislatures should carry out a viewpoint of sustainable port planning with the responsibilities, and regulators are given the right to mandate intervention.

7.0 Conclusion

Globalization and rapid sustainability issues force workers and scientists to construct positive and collaborative scheming for port longevity. Consistent or coherent port sustainability-oriented planning strategies are currently lacking. The green arch relates to the study and analysis of the current symbolic sustainability approaches to port planning. Previous ideas from our extensive literature review suggest that: the current approaches to port planning sustainability are confined to particular problems, historical data, and subjective opinions on the growth of the port itself; (2) long term port planning, eco-port planning approaches have given priority to environmental problems, but have overlooked the relevance of environmental issues; (3) modern sustainable port planning approaches aimed at meeting the demand of the present, and future generations are not following a right choice for sustainability; (4) The recommendation for green port planning has not taken into account for current and future generations; As a preferred commitment to achieving, we embraced green port planning with a study of the current sustainability strategies for port planning and offered more heedful implications for a better solution. This study provides a significant summary and persuades in-depth thought about longevity in ports to help authorities and learners appreciate the port durability scheme's present state.

Moreover, it requires a broader and more discussion on this issue to shift towards long-term sustainability eventually. In the future, the proposed green port system should implement follow-up approaches and plans from the planning regions, the planning goals, the planning processes, and the essential projects perspective. A well-arranged and supportive research-practice network will be helpful in port, shipping, and logistics. To achieve a deeper understanding of port sustainability planning, consideration will also be given to other elements through critical performance measures, such as economic effects and technological advances. Besides, there is a need to research ethics into existing research and procedures to inform other sustainability ports, encouraging creative thinking.

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